

VSD ethical and social values	Component	Hybrid AI Trustworthiness General Requirements	Priority
Human autonomy	Human agency	<p>Is the HAI implemented in the work and labour process? Consider task allocation between the HAI and humans for appropriate human oversight and control.</p> <p>Does the HAI enhance or augment human capabilities? Consider safeguards to prevent overconfidence/over-reliance in the results offered by the HAI.</p>	
	Human oversights	<p>What is the level of human control or involvement?</p> <p>Who is the human in control and what are the actions or tools for intervention? Consider mechanisms to ensure human control and oversight.</p> <p>Is the HAI a self-learning or autonomous system? Consider more specific mechanism of control and oversight.</p> <p>Consider detection and response mechanisms to assess whether something is going wrong.</p> <p>Consider a stop button or procedure to safely abort an operation where/when needed. Consider if this procedure aborts the process entirely, in part, or delegates control to a human.</p>	
Technical robustness and safety	Resilience to attack and security	<p>Consider to put measures in place to ensure the integrity and resilience of HAI against potential attacks.</p> <p>Consider how you system behave in unexpected situations and environments and what would be needed to mitigate a potential negative outcome.</p> <p>Implement mechanisms and measures to ensure the integrity and resilience of the HAI against potential cyberattacks.</p>	
	Fallback and general safety	<p>Consider creating a fallback plan for adversarial attacks or unexpected situations (including accidental or malicious misuse) and implementing the appropriate technical solutions (e.g. technical switching or asking for a human operator before proceeding).</p> <p>Consider the risk for human physical integrity (safety, accidental or malicious misuse) and how to mitigate the risk.</p>	
	Accuracy	<p>Consider what level and definition of accuracy would be required of the HAI in the context of the use cases.</p> <p>Consider mechanisms and measures to ensure the data is comprehensive and up to date.</p> <p>Consider mechanisms and measures in place to assess if there is a need for additional data in order to improve accuracy or eliminate bias.</p> <p>Consider mechanisms and measures to check if the HAI is making inaccurate predictions and ways to increase the system accuracy.</p>	
	Reliability and reproducibility	<p>Consider verification methods to measure and ensure different aspects of the HAI reliability and reproducibility in the use case scenario.</p> <p>Implement mechanisms/measures to assure the testing and verification of reliability of the HAI.</p> <p>Consider communication procedures to assure the user of the system reliability.</p>	
Privacy and data governance	Respect for privacy and data protection	<p>Does the HAI use personal data for training (including photos, video)? Take measures to enhance privacy via encryption, anonymisation and aggregation.</p> <p>Consider ways to develop and train the HAI without or with minimal use of potentially sensitive or personal data.</p> <p>Consider building in mechanisms for notice and control over personal data depending on the use case.</p>	
	Quality and integrity of data	<p>Consider aligning HAI with relevant standards (e.g. ISO, IEEE) for data management and governance.</p> <p>Consider oversight mechanisms for data collection, storage, processing and use.</p> <p>Implement a process to ensure the quality and integrity of the data; if the data is coming from external sources assess to what extent you are in control of the quality of the data; how are you verifying the dataset have not been compromised or hacked?</p>	
	Access to data	<p>Consider an oversight mechanism for logging when, where, how, by whom and for what purpose data was accessed.</p>	

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Transparency	Traceability	Consider measures/mechanisms to ensure traceability (which input data was gathered and selected and how the result occurred).	
	Explainability	Consider to what extent the decision, and hence the outcome, made by the HAI can be understood; to what degree the system's decision influences the decision-making process? Ensure an explanation as to why the system made a certain choice resulting in a particular outcome all the users can understand. Consider procedures to analyse the data and to update over time. Consider whether you can examine interpretability after the model training and development and whether you have access to the internal workflow of the model.	
	Communication	Implement measures/mechanisms to inform the users the reasons and criteria behind the HAI outcomes. Consider human psychology and potential limitations such as risk of confusion, confirmation bias or cognitive fatigue. Consider clear communication on characteristics, limitations and potential shortcomings of the HAI (including potential bias).	
Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness	Unfair bias avoidance	Consider an assessment of possible limitations arising from the composition of the used dataset. Consider the diversity and representativeness of HAI for specific population or problematic use cases. Implement a strategy or set of procedures to avoid creating or reinforcing unfair bias in the HAI (regarding the use of input data). Implement measures/mechanisms to allow the flagging of issues related to bias, discrimination or poor performance; establish clear steps of communicating on how and to whom such issues can be raised.	
	Accessibility and universal design	Consider if the system needs to accommodate different individual abilities.	
	Stakeholder participation	Consider a mechanism to include the participation of different stakeholders in the AI system's development and use.	
Societal and environmental wellbeing	Sustainable and environmentally friendly AI	Consider measures to ensure the environmental impact of deployment and use (type of energy) or the environmental impact of the HAI life cycle.	
	Social impact	Consider measure to ensure the social impacts of the HAI are well understood (e.g. risk of job loss, de-skilling of the workforce); implement measures to counteract such risks.	
	Society and democracy	Consider an assessment of the broader social impact of the HAI, such as potentially indirectly affecting stakeholders, chilling effects, surveillance.	
Accountability	Auditability	Consider mechanisms/measures to facilitate the system auditability (ensuring traceability and logging of the HAI processes and outcomes). Consider measures (especially in safety critical applications) that allows the HAI use and results to be audited independently.	
	Minimizing and reporting negative impact	Consider procedures (external guidance, auditing process) that support the overall accountability and ethics practices. Consider processes for third parties or workers to report potential vulnerabilities, risks or biases in the HAI.	
	Documenting trade-offs	Consider measures to identify relevant interests and values implicated by the use of HAI and potential trade-offs between them, and make sure the trade-off decision is documented.	
	Ability to redress	Consider mechanisms/measures that allow for redress in case of the occurrence of any harm or adverse impact.	
Awareness of misuse	Guard against all potential misuses and associated risks	Consider potential ways to misuse the HAI and the related outcomes (mission/function creep, accidental or malevolent use of HAI, surveillance, labelling of category of populations etc) and ways to minimise the risk.	
Competence	Provision of training for the users	Consider the types and levels of knowledge necessary to understand and operate the HAI; integrate safeguards against incompetent operation. Consider clear programs to provide information on the role of the operator, the competencies required and the implications of operator error. Consider provisions/programs of training on different levels of required competencies.	